

Post-hoc power analysis revealed that comparisons by program of study were underpowered. Specifically, the comparison between Physician Assistant and Nursing students (observed difference 12.3%) had only 42% power, while the Public Health vs. Nursing comparison (observed difference 8.8%) had 31% power. These findings should be interpreted as exploratory. In contrast, comparisons by gender (68% power), age (99% power), and year of study (>99% power) were adequately powered to detect the observed differences (Supplementary Table S2).

Table S2: Post-hoc power analysis for secondary comparisons of Mpox knowledge

Comparison	Sample sizes (n1, n2)	Observed difference	Achieved power ($\alpha=0.05$)	Interpretation
Physician Assistant vs. Nursing	66, 135	12.3%	42%	Underpowered; non-significant p-value inconclusive
Pharmacy vs. Nursing	159, 135	0.8%	5%	The observed difference between Pharmacy and Nursing students was 0.8%. The study had only 5% power to detect a difference of this magnitude, so the absence of a statistically significant difference should not be interpreted as evidence of equivalence. Larger studies are needed to compare knowledge across programmes.
Public Health vs. Nursing	45, 135	8.8%	31%	Underpowered; finding should be considered exploratory
Female vs. Male	285, 120	9.6%	68%	Adequately powered
Age 21-30 vs. <20	156, 208	18.2%	99%	Well-powered
Third-year vs. Second-year	324, 81	28.4%	>99%	Well-powered

Foot note: Power calculations performed using two-proportion z-test, two-tailed, $\alpha=0.05$.

